

FALSE FRIENDS IN LINGUISTICS; ENGLISH AND SPANISH COGNATES

Маманазарова Улугой Акрамжановна

E-mail: ulugoymamanazarova@gmail.com

Старший преподаватель кафедры «ОГиСЭД»

Филиал МГУ им. М.В. Ломоносова в г. Ташкенте

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False friends are words that look or sound similar in two languages but have different meanings. These can often lead to confusion and humorous mistranslations. Anyone who learns a foreign **language** needs to watch out for so-called false friends. No, they are not people who try to sabotage your effort by giving harmful advice. Let's just say for now that they cannot be treated lightly and can cause very serious problems in communication. In this article, we'll get into some details about this phenomenon and find false friends in various languages.

This term "false friends" was first introduced by Maxime Koessler and Jules Derocquigny in their 1928 book called *Les Faux Amis, ou les Trahisons du Vocabulaire Anglais* (which translates as *False Friends, or the Betrayals of English Vocabulary*). The term appears as *faux amis du traducteur* (false friend of a translator). However, it is its shortened version that gained popularity and became an official term used in linguistics.

False friends, also known as bilingual homophones, can be created in various ways. They can appear, for instance, as a result of shared etymology. If let's say, 3 languages inherited a word from a common ancestor and its meaning changed over time in at least one of them, we will face a false friend (being a native speaker of either one of the 2 remaining languages, of course). To illustrate the above, let's take a closer look at the examples of false friends in various languages.

One of the most common pairs of languages where false friends occur is English and Spanish.

Spanish and English have thousands of cognates, words that are the same in both languages, having the same etymology and similar meanings. But combinations such as *decepción* and "deception" are so-called false cognates — known more precisely as "false friends" or *falsos amigos* — word pairs that look like they might mean the same thing but don't. They can be confusing, and if you make the mistake of using them in speech or writing you're likely to be misunderstood.

Another example is the English word "embarrassed" which means feeling self-conscious or ashamed, while the Spanish word "embarazada" means pregnant.

One of the trickiest false friends between English and Spanish is the word "actually." In English, "actually" means "in reality" or "in fact." However, in Spanish, "actualmente" means "currently" or "at present." So, you can see how easily a miscommunication can occur if someone were to say "I am actually going to the store" in Spanish when they really meant to say "I am currently going to the store."

Another common false friend is the word "sensible." In English, "sensible" means having or showing good judgment. In Spanish, "sensible" means sensitive or emotionally intelligent. So, if someone were to say "he is very sensible" in English, they may mean that he is a practical and level-headed person, but in Spanish, it could be interpreted as him being emotionally sensitive.

There are hundreds of examples of false friends between these two pairs of languages. Here are just a few.

Actual (Spanish) - Current (English)

Carpeta (Spanish) - Folder (English)

Constipado (Spanish) - Constipated (English)

Embarazada (Spanish) - Embarrassed (English)

Fábrica (Spanish) - Fabric (English)

Ropa (Spanish) - Rope (English)

Sensible (Spanish) - Sensible (English)

Tuna (Spanish) - Tuna (English)

It's important to be aware of false friends when learning a new language, as they can lead to miscommunications and misunderstandings. Just because two words look or sound alike doesn't mean they have the same meaning in different languages. It's always a good idea to double-check the meaning of a word before using it in conversation, especially when dealing with false friends.

Overall, false friend words between English and Spanish can be tricky to navigate, but with awareness and practice, you can easily avoid any mix-ups and confidently communicate in both languages.

Literature:

1. [www.False Friends in Spanish and English \(thoughtco.com\)](http://www.FalseFriendsinSpanishandEnglish(thoughtco.com))
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